

**"MOTIVATIONAL FEATURES OF THE USE OF LITERATURE SOURCES IN
TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS-PHILOLOGISTS"**

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The reliability of the results of the study is ensured by the complexity of the analysis of the problem in determining the initial theoretical and methodological principles of its study; consistency of empirical and theoretical methods adequate to the goals and objectives of the study; a combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data obtained; application of methods of mathematical statistics; experimental verification of the provisions that made up the research hypothesis; representativeness of the sample of experimental and control groups of students.

The scientific novelty of the study is as follows: the features of the formation of motivation for learning a foreign language among students of non-linguistic specialties are revealed; pedagogical conditions are revealed that contribute to the formation of positive motivation for learning a foreign language among students of non-linguistic specialties; a set of pedagogical tools has been developed that contributes to the development of motivation for learning a foreign language among future specialists in a university setting.

The theoretical significance of the work is determined by the fact that the possibilities of applying and adapting the principles of a new direction of teaching English in Western pedagogy - "English for Special Purposes" (ESP) to the conditions of Russian education are identified; the levels of formation of motivation for learning a foreign language are determined and characterized, the criteria and indicators of the formation of motives in the study of a foreign language among students of non-linguistic specialties are supplemented. The practical significance of the study is as follows: a system of measures has been developed that ensures the development of motivation for learning a foreign language among students of non-linguistic specialties; f - a set of methods has been compiled to determine the formation of the motivation for learning a foreign language; English language training programs have been developed at the Faculty of Psychology, taking into account the requirements of the future specialty within contextual learning and "English for Special Purposes"; Methodological recommendations for conducting classes have been drawn up.

The formation of the motivation for learning a foreign language among future specialists is facilitated by various pedagogical tools developed within the framework of three models: semiotic, imitation and social. The models are interrelated and can be used in one sequence or another, starting with a semiotic model or a social model, depending on the course and the level of students' preparedness. The semiotic model includes communicative exercises for mastering vocabulary, grammar within the topic; work with the main texts, communicative exercises for the main texts. The simulation model provides for the development of speech clichés and clichés, work with texts that are additional to those contained in the traditional program, and communicative exercises for them; teaching the skills of dialogic communication; development of professional-speech situations of role-playing behavior; filling out questionnaires of a psychological nature; poster / oral presentations. The social model includes role-playing games, business games, case studies, simulations, written forms of work. The three models described above provide for joint goal-setting (students and the teacher jointly set goals, taking into account the motives of a particular group); personalization of the lesson (it becomes personally significant); formation of a competent specialist (professional context makes it possible to form some professional qualities).

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